

Abstract

Potential Therapeutic Properties of *Olea Europaea* Leaves from Selected Cultivars Based on Their Mineral and Organic Profiles.

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Abstract

Background: Interest in complementary therapies, such as functional nutrition and phytotherapy, has grown significantly, influenced by the global dissemination of knowledge from Oriental herbal medicine. This shift is further driven by an emerging economic paradigm moving from linear to circular models, where agricultural by-products are upcycled into value-added therapeutic applications. Various parts of Western plants, particularly olive leaves (*Olea europaea* L.), are increasingly consumed as extracts, infusions, or whole powders due to their documented health benefits.

Objective: This study evaluated the antimicrobial potential of olive leaf extracts derived from three distinct Portuguese cultivars—Cobrançosa, Madural, and Verdeal. The samples were sourced from a mixed-cultivation olive grove located in Vale de Salgueiros, Portugal, to assess their efficacy against a range of Gram-positive (+) and Gram-negative (-) bacteria.

Methods: The antimicrobial activity of the leaf extracts was measured using the agar diffusion assay. The extracts were tested against Gram-positive strains (*S. aureus*, *S. epidermidis*, *B. cereus*) and Gram-negative strains (*P. aeruginosa*, *Salmonella Enteritidis*, and *E. coli*).

Results: All three cultivars exhibited antimicrobial activity against Gram-negative *P. aeruginosa* and *Salmonella Enteritidis*, as well as Gram-positive *B. cereus*. Only the Verdeal cultivar demonstrated activity against *S. aureus*. None of the extracts showed significant inhibitory effects against *S. epidermidis* or *E. coli*.

Conclusions: Overall, the leaves of Portuguese *O. europaea* cultivars demonstrated effective antimicrobial properties against several prevalent bacterial strains. These findings suggest significant potential for their use in therapeutic formulations for both human and veterinary medicine, as well as their application as natural preservatives in the food and cosmetic industries.

Keywords: *Olea Europaea*; Herbal Medicine; Antimicrobial Potential.

Citation: de Oliveira N., Criado M.B., Machado J., Chéu M.H., Lopes L., Barroso M.F., Silva A., Sousa S., Domingues V., Grosso C. Potential Therapeutic Properties of *Olea Europaea* Leaves from Selected Cultivars Based on Their Mineral and Organic Profiles. Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health. 2026;4(2) 10.5281/zenodo.19889187

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Acknowledgements: This work was presented at the 1st Scientific Seminars of Complementary Therapies in Health, on 10 October 2025.